

Studies of ultrafast reaction dynamics in the excited states of molecules in solution^ψ

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In the course of a photochemical reaction, reactants are converted into products with the possibility of various transition states and transient intermediates on the reaction pathway. The properties of these transient intermediate species are central to the reaction and determine its rate and selectivity. Lifetimes of these intermediates vary from a few tens of a femtosecond to a few picoseconds. In condensed phase chemical reactions, the dynamics of solute-solvent interaction also play a significant role in determining the fate of the transients and intermediates, and hence the rates of the chemical reactions undergone by them. Ultrafast transient absorption spectroscopic techniques developed in our laboratory have enabled us to investigate the numerous number of intra- and intermolecular processes undergone by the excited states and the other intermediate species produced following optical excitation of a solute molecule in condensed phase with femto and picosecond time resolution. This presentation discusses briefly the results of our studies on the excited state dynamics and photophysical and photochemical processes in LDS-821 dye and fullerene molecules in solution and also the bond-breaking dynamics of HgI₂ in ethanol solution.

One of the fundamental and important questions in chemistry is to understand *Alchemy*, i.e. building and breaking of molecules. Cracking of molecules is possible by adding energy to the molecules from lasers. However, the bond-breaking process is controlled by the laws of statistical thermodynamics¹. This reveals the fact that as soon as the energy is supplied to the molecule onto any of its modes or bonds by any means, this energy is dissipated or distributed among the different vibrational modes very quickly following the laws of Boltzmann distribution and hence destroying the possibility of selectivity in bond-breaking process. Now an important question is that whether it is possible to bypass the laws of statistical thermodynamics if we use intense ultrashort laser to supply the energy to a particular bond, which we want to break, in a time-scale shorter than that in which energy dissipation takes place and break that particular bond of the molecule at our will before the other parts of it feel the event. If we could achieve success in this direction, the laser-induced chemistry will have a great potentiality in the field of isotope separation, synthesis of new materials as well as in medicine. The question of breaking molecular bonds selectively has opened the door to many fundamental questions : What is the time required to break a bond? How quickly the excess energy deposited in a molecule is distributed among its different vibrational modes or dissipated to the environment? What are the rates for different kinds of in-

tramolecular motions, such as electron, proton, and atom transfer processes, or the conformational relaxation processes? It has also been observed that many of these processes occur in nature with awesome rapidity and with almost unit efficiency². For example, during the process of photosynthesis in bacterial reaction center, the electron travels about 17 Å over the molecular distance in 3 picosecond^{2,3}. It has been a challenge for the photochemists and the biophysicists to understand this photoinduced electron transfer process and mimic the system for the purpose of storing the solar energy. However, the best of the man-made systems could not achieve more than 10 percent efficiency due to very efficient back electron transfer process⁴. Another important natural process is the photoisomerization of retinal chromophore in bacteriorhodopsin. This process represents the dynamics of the first step of vision process and has been shown to be complete within 200 fs⁵.

This discussion reveals that in order to study the mechanism of many of the important natural processes occurring under the influence of light, we need the techniques having ultrafast time resolution, say pico and femto seconds. The laser technology has undergone a tremendous development in the last two or three decades to generate laser pulses as short as 5 fs duration⁶ and the photochemists and photophysicists have always been in the frontline to use these lasers as their tool for investigating the mechanism of fast and ultrafast photoinduced processes⁷.

^ψRev. Fr. L. M. Yeddanapalli Memorial Lecture (1999) delivered at the 37th. Annual Convention of Chemists, organised under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society, on November 16, 2000 at Hardwar.

In our laboratory, we designed and developed the laser kinetic absorption spectrometers, which provide time resolution ranging from a few hundred femtoseconds (fs) to a few milliseconds (ms). These spectrometers have been used to investigate the photo and radiation chemical processes in a variety of chemical systems, such as fullerenes⁸⁻¹⁹, hydroxy and amino substituted ketones²⁰⁻²³ and diketones²⁴, laser dyes²⁵ etc., with the time resolutions ranging from a few microseconds down to a couple of hundred femtosecond. Here we shall discuss briefly a few of the chemical systems studied recently by our group.

Picosecond transient absorption spectrometer :

Details of this spectrometer are available in references 20 and 22. Briefly, the second (532 nm) or third (355 nm) harmonic output pulses of 35 ps duration from an active-passive mode-locked Nd : YAG laser (Continuum, model 501-C-10) were used for excitation of the samples. Continuum probe pulses in the 400–920 nm region were generated by focusing the residual fundamental in a H₂O : D₂O mixture (50 : 50). The probe pulses were delayed with respect to the pump pulses using a 1-m long linear motion translation stage and the transient absorption spectra at different delay times (upto 6 ns) were recorded by an optical multichannel analyzer interfaced to an IMB-PC. Transients surviving beyond 50 ns were studied by monitoring their absorption using a tungsten filament lamp in combination with a Bausch and Lomb monochromator (f/10, 350–800 nm), Hamamatsu R 928 PMT and a 500 MHz digital storage oscilloscope (Tektronix, TDS-540A) connected to a PC.

Subpicosecond transient absorption spectrometer :

The informations on the dynamics of interest occurring on a time-scale faster than 50 ps have been obtained using a home-built sub-picosecond transient absorption spectrometer, the block diagram of which has been shown in Fig. 1. This can be described here in brief as follows. The 100 pJ

pulses of 70 fs duration at 620 nm generated in an argon ion pumped colliding pulse mode-locked (CPM) dye laser, were amplified to about 100 μ J pulses of 100 fs duration in a five-stage dye amplifier pumped by a Nd : YAG laser (280 mJ at 532 nm, 30 Hz). About 10% of the energy output from the amplifier was used to excite the sample taken in a flow through cell of 2 mm path-length. The residual fundamental was used to generate the white light continuum (400–950 nm) in a flowing water medium of 1 cm path-length. The transient absorption spectra were recorded using a dual diode array based optical multichannel analyzer and the decay dynamics at a particular wavelength region (10 nm width) were monitored using two photodiodes coupled with the boxcar integrators. The overall time resolution of the absorption spectrometer was determined to be about 300 fs by measuring the growth of the negative absorption signal at 650 nm due to bleaching in the ground state for malachite green in ethylene glycol and the same was used to determine the zero delay position between the pump and the probe pulses. The temporal dynamics were analyzed by fitting the temporal profile of the decay dynamics monitored at any wavelength by iterative deconvolution with the instrument response function of Sech² type having FWHM of 300 fs. The details of the spectrometer having time resolution of about 50 fs, are available in references 26 and 27.

Dynamics of chemical bond-breaking process in solution²⁶

In introduction, we raised two important and fundamental questions : what is the time required to break a chemical bond in a photo-dissociation process, and how the energy supplied to the molecule is partitioned between the fragments and the different kinds of motions of the fragments, such as kinetic, rotational and vibrational. Here, we discuss an example of the laser induced bond-breaking process – the photodissociation dynamics of mercuric iodide (HgI₂) in ethanol solution,

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the subpicosecond transient absorption spectrometer : (M) mirror, (G) grating, (BS) beam splitter, (L) lens, (SH) sample holder, (SA) saturable absorber, (CG) continuum generation, (IF) interference filter, (T) beam block, (PD) photodiode detector, (P) $\lambda/4$ plate; (LSU) laser synchronisation unit.

When HgI_2 is excited by 330 nm light to one of its dissociative higher electronic excited states (HgI_2^*), the molecule is dissociated to the fragments, vibrationally hot HgI ($\text{HgI}^\#$) and I^{10} . In this process, the $\text{HgI}^\#$ fragment is produced in the ground electronic state ($X^2 \Sigma^+$)²⁸, but with a large amount of excess vibrational energy. The iodine atom is also produced in the ground electronic state. The excess vibrational energy in $\text{HgI}^\#$ is subsequently dissipated to the surrounding solvent bath by external vibrational relaxation (EVR) or vibrational cooling process. Using the transient absorption technique we have been able to follow-up the dynamics of the bond-breaking and energy flow process in the photodissociation reaction of HgI_2 in ethanol solution.

HgI_2 , being a tri-atomic linear molecule, has four fundamental modes : one symmetric stretch, one asymmetric stretch and two degenerate bending modes corresponding to the frequencies 155, 237 and 33 cm^{-1} , respectively²⁹. Symmetric stretch and bending modes are bound motions but asymmetric stretch can provide the dissociative motion. This mode has the fundamental frequency, $\nu_0 = 237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and its time period of oscillation is 141 fs. On excitation of HgI_2 molecule onto one of the excited electronic dissociative state, the HgI_2^* system evolves along the dissociative potential energy surface. This motion can be described as

Fig. 2. Potential energy diagram depicting the photodissociation dynamics of HgI_2 . On photoexcitation by 300 nm photon, the molecules of HgI_2 are lifted from the ground state to one of the electronic excited state which is dissociative in nature. The excited molecule evolves in this dissociative surface and dissociates into I and HgI fragments. During the course of the dissociation process the molecular species having different I-HgI bond distances can be described as the 'transition states'. When the I-HgI bond distance lengthens beyond 5 Å, the bond can be considered dissociated.

the separation of the HgI and I fragments due to stretching of one of the Hg-I bonds due to asymmetric stretch motion (Fig. 2). When the separation between the two fragments reaches about 5 Å, they become free from each other's influence and the molecule is considered to have been dissociated into two fragments²⁹. Different molecular configurations of IHg-I , having different internuclear separations between the I and HgI fragments, existing at times in between the two processes, photoexcitation and dissociation, can be designated as the transition states. After creation of HgI_2^* state on photoexcitation, it is possible to probe the transition states as well as the dissociated fragments or the product states, $\text{HgI}^\#$ and I, using probe light of appropriate color. In our experiment we have used 330 nm pump and probe pulses in the wavelength range 400–700 nm, both the laser pulses having 50 fs duration. However, to be brief, we will discuss only the results obtained from the experiments using 330 nm pump and 330 and 660 nm probe pulses, which we will designate as 330/330 and 330/660 experiments, respectively, to explain the photodissociation and energy flow dynamics in the said process.

Let us make a simple calculation to illustrate the fact that the photodissociation process is really very fast and have a rough estimate of the time taken to break the I-HgI bond in the photodissociation process. The excitation energy due to a single photon of 330 nm wavelength is 33303 cm^{-1} and the energy required to photodissociate the I-HgI bond^{28,29} is 21000 cm^{-1} . Hence the energy of recoil with which the fragments are moving away from each other is 9303 cm^{-1} . So the velocity of the fragments with which they are getting separated is, $v = (2E_{\text{recoil}}/\mu)^{1/2} = 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, where μ is the reduced mass of the separated fragments. If the bond is said to have broken when the fragments travel away by about 5 Å or $5 \times 10^{-13} \text{ km}$ apart from each other, the bond dissociation time is calculated to be about 250 fs.

Fig. 3. Transient absorption signals for (a) 330/660 experiment over an extended time-scale and (b) 330/330 experiment, due to photolysis of HgI_2 in ethanol.

The temporal dynamics of the transient absorption recorded in the 330/660 experiment due to photolysis of HgI_2 in ethanol is shown in Fig. 3a. This is due to $\text{HgI}^\#$ species, which absorbs in the visible region (400–700 nm)²⁶. The results of 330/330 nm bleaching experiment is presented in Fig. 3b. At $t = 0$ ps, this signal shows a strong coherent spike typically seen in experiments of this kind. This prohibits the direct observation of the dynamics for times less than 100 fs. As the probe delay is increased, the absorbance signal becomes negative with increasing delay as a result of the photo-depletion of the parent molecule. This bleach of 3 mOD persists throughout the time-scale of our measurements of the temporal dynamics in the 330/660 experiment and no recovery has been observed. The magnitude of the bleaching signal, while considered the molar absorptivity of HgI_2 at 330 nm, the concentrations of HgI_2 used and the intensity of the pump light pulse, is consistent with a quantum yield of photodissociation of HgI_2 , is approximately equal to unity and there is no sign of recombination to produce back HgI_2 .

The most important and interesting feature of the temporal dynamics of $\text{HgI}^\#$, as shown in Fig. 4, is an oscillatory component of the signal superimposed on the decay of $\text{HgI}^\#$. The oscillatory component of the signal persists for a few hundred fs. The total decay dynamics of $\text{HgI}^\#$ has been modeled with the response function,

$$\text{OD}(t) = A \exp(-t/\tau_A) \cos(\omega t + \pi) + B \exp(-t/\tau_B) \quad (2)$$

A and B are amplitude factors, τ_A is the damping time constant for the oscillation amplitude, ω and π are frequency and phase of the oscillatory component and τ_B is the population decay time of the transient species. The best-fit parameters obtained are: $A/B = 1.71$; $\tau_A = 330 \pm 33$ fs; $\omega/2\pi c = 89.5 \pm 15$ cm^{-1} ; $\tau_B = 2.75 \pm 0.27$ ps. The temporal dynamics as shown in Fig. 3a is fitted very well to a single exponential function with lifetime of 2.72 ± 0.2 ps. The most probable interpretation of the features observed in Fig. 4 is that they arise from the modulated absorption of $\text{HgI}^\#$. The oscillation arise due to the fact that following photodissociation of HgI_2 , $\text{HgI}^\#$ is created in a coherent superposition of vibrational states, which is popularly known as 'wave packet'. The wave packet then oscillates between the classical turning points of the potential energy surface of the ground electronic state of the $\text{HgI}^\#$ species causing the 660 nm absorption to be tuned in and out of resonance between the ground electronic state and one of its excited state (Fig. 5). Using the gas phase PES of HgI , an estimate of the energy content and distribution in the diatomic photoproduct may be ascertained. The fundamental frequency and anharmonicity constant of the stretching vibration of the only mode of Hg-I , are 126 and 1.3 cm^{-1} , respectively³⁰. Calculation shows that the beats correspond to a vibrational frequency of $ca \nu = 15$ and that the ob-

Fig. 4. Dynamics of the transient absorption recorded at early time for 330/660 experiment due to photolysis of HgI_2 in ethanol.

served signal originates mainly from a fragment which is born with $ca 1700$ cm^{-1} of excess (mean) vibrational energy. The remaining photolysis energy ($ca 7600$ cm^{-1}) must then be distributed among the translational and rotational motions of the fragments as well as the associated solvent motions. The frequency of the wave packet oscillations represents the mean frequency of a distribution of vibrational states determined by the initial conditions. Finally, the overall signal decay with lifetime τ_B , which is 2.7 ps, should be due to solvent induced vibrational relaxation (EVR) process undergone by $\text{HgI}^\#$. The phase of the wave packet has been found to be π radian. This result suggests that when Hg-I bond is compressed, the molecule does not absorb at 660 nm. If the Hg-I bond in the nascent product HgI is compressed, such as would occur in a dissociation reaction producing I and HgI from HgI_2 through the asymmetric stretching coordinate (Fig. 2), the resulting wave packet would not be detected until it would move to the attractive turning point of the ground state PES. Hence this would yield a phase shift of π for the absorption signal, as observed in Fig. 5.

From this study, the following conclusions have been drawn: in photolysis of HgI_2 by 330 nm laser pulses of 50 fs duration, HgI is produced in a coherent superposition of vibrational levels on the ground electronic state. The mean excess vibrational energy corresponds to about 1700 cm^{-1} . This excess vibrational energy is dissipated to the solvent with an average lifetime of about 2.7 ps. The photolysis yield is near unity.

Photophysical and electron transfer properties of fullerenes⁸⁻¹⁸

In recent years, buckminsterfullerene, C_{60} and its derivatives have shown very promising applications in non-linear optics and optoelectronics, photovoltaic cells and also in biology³¹⁻³³. C_{60} is considered to be an efficient photosensitizing agent in photodynamic therapy because of its ability to produce the triplet state with unit efficiency under photoexcitation⁸. Fullerenes also show various interesting properties, such as superconductivity, ferromagnetism and photoconductivity when they are chemically treated with some electron donors or acceptors³³⁻³⁵. However, all of the applications mentioned above require a good

Fig. 5. Coherent oscillations of vibrational 'wave packet' in the ground electronic state of HgI ($X^2 \Sigma_g^+$) produced due to photolysis of HgI₂ by 330 nm light pulse of 50 fs duration. HgI is produced with excess vibrational energy at $ca v = 15$ and with the nuclear configuration corresponding to the position A on the ground state surface. 660 nm probe light is absorbed by the nascent vibrationally hot HgI species (HgI^{*}) only when it reaches the configuration corresponding to the position B during the course of its vibrational motion.

knowledge of the photophysical and photochemical properties of their excited states which are responsible for those important properties. Investigations in recent years have confirmed that the nature of the functional groups and the degree of functionalization of the fullerene molecule severely affect its physicochemical properties and hence the fullerene chemistry has also been developed for introducing

different organic functional groups into the molecule. The physicochemical properties of these fullerene derivatives have been shown to be very different from pristine C₆₀ and this effect has been rationalized in terms of the perturbation of the electron distribution on the surface of the spherical molecule due to the presence of the functional groups. In this presentation we like to discuss the photophysical and photochemical properties of a few of the fullerene derivatives studied recently in our laboratory.

Photophysics of C₆₀, monochloropentaphenylfullerene [C₆₀(C₆H₅)₅Cl, MCPPF], pentaphenylfulleren-2-ol [C₆₀(C₆H₅)₅OH, PPF], penta-4-fluorophenylfulleren-2-ol [C₆₀(C₆H₄F)₅OH, PFPF] :

C₆₀, MCPPF, PPF and PFPF are soluble in benzene, toluene, benzonitrile and alkane solvents, sparingly soluble in acetonitrile, but insoluble in water. The positions of the absorption peaks of the fullerenes are given in Table 1. The absence of the broad and relatively strong absorption band in the 440–670 nm region in the absorption spectra of these fullerene derivatives but in that of C₆₀, suggests that the presence of the functional groups has considerably distorted the electronic structure of the parent molecule. These derivatives have been seen to be about ten times stronger fluorescent than that of C₆₀. Emission maxima and the quantum yields of fluorescence of these two derivatives in benzene and benzonitrile are given in Table 1 along with that of C₆₀ in benzene for comparison. Higher yields of fluorescence for the derivatives indicate perturbation of the symmetry properties of the electronic structure of C₆₀. The other photophysical parameters, such as the lifetimes of the

Table 1. Photophysical properties of C₆₀, PPF, PFPF and MCPPF

Parameter	C ₆₀	PPF	PFPF	MCPPF
$\lambda_{\max} (S_0 \rightarrow S_n)$ nm (in BZ)	231, 257, 329, 440–670	215, 231, 255, 350 (sh), 395 (sh), 460 (sh)	215, 231, 255, 350 (sh), 395 (sh), 460 (sh)	232, 255, 340 (sh), 390 (sh)
$\lambda_{\max} (em)$ nm (BZ)	740	650	650	–
Φ_f (BZ or BN)	$\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}$ (BZ)	0.7×10^{-3} (BZ); 1.2×10^{-3} (BN)	0.7×10^{-3} (BZ); 0.9×10^{-3} (BN)	–
τ_s , ns (BZ or BN)	1.3 (BZ)	1.2 ± 0.2 (BZ); 1.9 ± 0.1 (BN)	1.0 (BZ); 1.5 (BN)	1.6 (BZ)
$\lambda_{\max} (S_1 \rightarrow S_n)$, nm ($\epsilon, dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$) (BZ)	480 (3000), 880 (6300)	610 (3100 \pm 1000), 900 (7300 \pm 1000)	610 (3200), 900 (7250)	600, 880 (9000)
$\lambda_{\max} (T_1 \rightarrow T_n)$ nm ($\epsilon, dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	510 (3000); 740 (14000) (BZ);	650 (14500) (BZ); 670 (BN)	650 (13000) (BZ); 670 (BN)	670 (20000) (BZ)
Φ_T	0.95 ± 0.05 (BZ)	0.49 ± 0.03 (BZ); 0.45 ± 0.03 (BN)	0.61 ± 0.03 (BZ); 0.63 ± 0.03 (BN)	0.45 (BZ)
τ_T μs	260 (BZ)	86 ± 2 (BZ); 112 ± 5 (BN)	95 (BZ); 150 (BN)	110 (BZ)
k_{TS_3} $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	2.0×10^8 (BZ)	2.3×10^8 (BZ)	1.2×10^8 (BZ)	5.8×10^8 (BZ)
k_{TT_3} $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	1.8×10^9 (BZ)	8.0×10^9 (BZ); 3.2×10^{10} (BN)	7.0×10^9 (BZ); 1.2×10^{10} (BN)	6×10^9 (BZ)

singlet and triplet states and wavelength maxima of excited singlet and triplet state absorptions of these fullerenes have also been presented in Table 1.

The decay kinetics of the photolytically generated triplets of these fullerenes follow good first order kinetics in both the solvents, benzene and benzonitrile, when the initial concentrations of the triplets produced are very low ($\sim 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³). However, the decay kinetics of the triplets are not purely single exponential but follow mixed first and second order kinetics, when the higher concentrations of the triplets are initially produced ($< 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³).

Hence, it is expected that in addition to the normal first order decay of the triplet to the ground state (eq. 3), other possible processes contributing to the decay might include the triplet-triplet annihilation (eq. 4) and quenching of the triplet by the ground state (eq. 5). All these three rate constants, k_T ($= \tau_T^{-1}$), k_{TS} and k_{TT} have been determined and given in Table 1.

Electron transfer properties of the fullerenes :

Fullerenes, which have high electron affinities (2.6–2.8 eV), form very weak charge-transfer complex (CT) with the amines in the ground state. The ground state equilibrium constants for the formation of CT complex, determined by using the Benesi-Heldebrand equation³⁶, are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Electron transfer properties of PPF and PFPF

Fullerene	Donor	K_{CT} , dm ³ mol ⁻¹	ϵ_{CT} (600 nm), dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	k_{ET} , dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	τ_{GR} , ps	k_{BET} , 10 ¹⁰ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
C ₆₀	DPA	0.04	2000		240	
	TPA	0.05	1500		1300	
MCPFF	DPA	0.6	4670		300	
	TPA	0.3	9300		130	
PPF	DPA	0.75	350	1.27		11.2 ± 0.3
	TPA			1.16		6.3 ± 0.3
PFPF	DPA	2.3	360	1.10		22.5 ± 0.5

The dynamics of charge transfer in the excited CT complex as well as in the excited singlet state have been investigated by picosecond (ps) laser flash photolysis on excitation at 532 nm. Excitation of the solutions containing the fullerene derivatives and the amines in benzonitrile by this light does not excite the amines but the CT complex and the free fullerene molecules present in solution. Also biphotonic ionization of these amines could be avoided by keeping the laser energy fluence low.

Fig. 6 shows the time-resolved transient absorption spectra obtained on ps laser flash photolysis of the solution containing C₆₀ and 0.3 mol dm⁻³ of TPA in benzonitrile. The spectrum recorded immediately after the laser pulse

Fig. 6. Time-resolved absorption spectra of the transients produced due to photolysis of a solution containing C₆₀ and 0.3 mol dm⁻³ of TPA in benzene by 532 nm laser pulses of 35 ps duration. The spectra are recorded at (1) 0, (2) 0.5, (3) 1, (4) 2, (5) 3 and (6) 6 ns after the laser pulse.

(curve 1) has two distinct bands with maxima at ca 650 and 890 nm. The decay of the transient absorption, either at 650 or 890 nm, is seen to follow first order kinetics with a lifetime of 1.3 ns (curve 'a' in inset of Fig. 6) and could be assigned to the cation radical of TPA (TAP^{•+}) and the anion radical of C₆₀^{•-}, respectively. These cation and anion radicals are present in an ion-pair (IP), which is formed due to charge separation in the excited CT complex. The disappearance of the cation and anion radicals with time can be assigned to the geminate recombination process in the ion-pair leading to the formation of the triplet state of C₆₀ (³C₆₀^{*}) having absorption maximum at 740 nm.

To investigate the interaction between the triplet states of these fullerene derivatives with the amines, the laser flash photolysis study in the microsecond time-domain was performed in the presence of low concentrations ($\sim 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) of the amines in benzonitrile. Fig. 7 shows the time resolved transient absorption spectra obtained due to photolysis of PPF (1.2×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) in benzonitrile in

Fig. 7. Time-resolved transient absorption spectra recorded at (a) 1 and (b) 30 μs after photolysis of a solution of PPF and 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ of DPA in benzene by 532 nm laser pulses of 35 ps duration. The inset shows the second order decay kinetics monitored at 670 nm.

Fig. 8. (a) Steady state absorption spectra, (b) emission spectra in solid matrices at 77 K and (C) fluorescence spectra at room temperature in DMSO.

77 K. The gross features of these spectra are more or less similar in other solvents studied (Table 3). The absorption spectra are structureless and broad, having half-widths of about 4000 cm^{-1} . The emission spectra in each solvent recorded at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures are significantly different, the former ones being very much red-shifted with respect to the latter ones. The maximum of the emission spectrum recorded in each of the solvents at room temperature shows a large red-shift, more than *ca* 180 nm with respect to the absorption maximum in the corresponding solvent. The large Stokes' shift between the maxima of the absorption and emission spectra recorded at room temperature indicates that certainly the Franck-Condon (FC) excited state is not the emitting state. The steady state fluorescence maximum also shifts to red due to increase in solvent polarity. Fluorescence quantum yields and the lifetimes determined in different solvents are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Time constants of LDS-821

Solvent	ϕ_f	τ_f , ps	τ_g , ps	$\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{soln}}$, ps	$\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{vac}}$, ps ^a
CF	0.10	1030	4.0	—	2.8
DCM	0.105	1340	1.8	2.1	0.5
ACN	0.035	570	1.5	1.5	0.26
DMSO	0.045	558	4.0	2.5	1.79
MeOH	0.038	350	2.0	1.8	5.0
Ethanol	0.04	400	6.5	3.6	16
Propanol	0.041	500	16	10.6	26
Butanol	0.03	585	14	11.1	63
Pentanol	0.05	675	22	20	103
Ethylene glycol	0.021	300	17	17.1	15.0

^aThese values are from Refs. 45 and 49.

Absorption characteristics of the transient species produced due to photolysis of LDS-821 by 532 nm laser pulses of 35 ps duration have been studied in a set of solvents. Fig. 9 shows one of the typical results of the transient

Fig. 9. Time-resolved transient absorption spectra of LDS-821 in 2-propanol due to excitation by 532 nm laser pulses of 35 ps duration (2 mJ/pulse). The time windows at which the spectra are recorded are (1) 0, (2) 120, (3) 200, (4) 260, (5) 330, (6) 460, (7) 600, (8) 800, (9) 1000, (10) 1300 and (11) 1650 ps. See the text for identification of the different spectral bands. One of the insets shows the first order plot for the decay of the stimulated emission intensity monitored at 815 nm. The other inset shows the stimulated emission spectra of LDS-821 in different solvents recorded at zero ps time delay. Spectra 1 to 5 are in chloroform, ethanol, acetonitrile, methanol and DMSO. To show the Gaussian shape of the spectral band, the Gaussian fit only to the spectrum in DMSO is shown.

absorption studies of LDS-821 in 2-propanol in picosecond time-domain. The features of the time-resolved transient absorption spectra in other solvents are seen to be more or less similar. The absorption spectrum of the transient species recorded immediately after the 35 ps laser pulse has several features. It is characterized by two positive absorption bands, i.e. bands having positive absorbance values, with maxima at 540 and 720 nm and two negative absorption bands, i.e. bands having negative absorbance values, with maxima at 620 and 815 nm. The two positive absorption bands are due to excited state absorption (ESA). The negative absorption band in the 570–700 nm region, which corresponds to the visible absorption band in the ground state absorption spectrum of LDS-821 (Fig. 8), should be due to bleaching of the ground state molecules following optical excitation and its recovery with time indicates the return of the molecules to the ground state after relaxation of the molecules from the excited state (or states). The other negative absorption band in the 750–950 nm region, overlapping with that of the steady state fluorescence spectra at room temperature, may be assigned to the gain or the emission stimulated by the continuum probe pulse from the fluorescing state.

The rate of decrease of the stimulated emission intensity measured at 815 nm has been observed to be nearly the same (within experimental error of about 5%) as that of the decay of the transient absorption monitored at 540 nm as well as the rate of bleaching recovery monitored at 600 nm. The lifetimes of the transient species obtained from these measurements have also been seen to agree well within experimental error with those determined by single photon

counting technique. The isosbestic points in between the positive and negative absorption bands indicate that at any time after about 35 ps of photo-excitation, only two states, namely, the ground and the fluorescing states, are responsible for the entire spectrum and the ground state recovers almost completely after relaxation from the fluorescing state. Hence, this fact excludes the possibility of formation

Fig. 10. Time-resolved transient (absorption/stimulated emission) spectra of LDS-821 in chloroform due to excitation at 620 nm. The spectra are recorded at (1) 0.5, (2) 1 and (3) 15 ps time-delays after the pump pulse. The inset shows the temporal evolution of the transient absorption/stimulated emission at 730 and 800 nm. At 730 nm the stimulated emission grows with a lifetime of 1 ps followed by a decay with lifetime of 4.5 ps. At 800 nm the stimulated emission grows with a lifetime of 4.2 ps.

of any other intermediate in between these two states, say the triplet state or any other isomers in the excited state. The maxima of the stimulated emission bands recorded in different solvents have shown significant solvent dependence, e.g. the maxima are at 800 and 842 nm in chloroform (CF) and DMSO, respectively (inset of Fig. 9).

Fig. 10 shows the absorption spectra of the transient recorded at 0.5, 1 and 15 ps following photo-excitation of LDS-821 in chloroform solution by 620 nm laser pulses of subpicosecond duration. In addition to the positive and negative absorption bands at 550 and 650 nm, respectively, the transient spectrum recorded at 0.5 ps is characterized by another weak negative absorption band having a peak at *ca* 750 nm, occurring due to weak emission from the excited state (curve 1 in Fig. 10). This emission grows up initially and then decays with a concomitant development of a new emission band having a peak at 800 nm. The latter continues to grow up to about 15 ps with no shift of the wavelength maxima of the stimulated emission band with time. The temporal evolution of the transient absorbance has been followed at 730 and 800 nm and has been shown in the inset of Fig. 10. The growth and decay lifetime of the stimulated emission measured at 730 nm are 1 ± 0.2 and 4.5 ± 0.4 ps, respectively. The growth lifetime of the stimulated emission intensity monitored at 800 nm is 4.2 ± 0.2 ps. The

Fig. 11. Time-resolved transient spectra of LDS-821 in ACN due to excitation at 620 nm. The spectra are recorded at (1) 0.5, (2) 0.7, (3) 1, (4) 1.5, (5) 2, (6) 3, (7) 4, (8) 6 and (9) 10 ps time delays after the pump pulse. The inset shows the evolution of the stimulated emission spectra in 650–930 nm region, recorded at (a) 0.5, (b) 0.7, (c) 1 and (d) 12 ps time delays, as they have been normalized to approximately the same intensity at the wavelength maximum.

good agreement between the decay lifetime of the stimulated emission measured at 730 nm and the growth lifetime measured at 800 nm indicates that the state or the species having the stimulated emission band centered at 800 nm is formed due to decay of the state or the species having emission band centered at 750 nm.

Fig. 12. The temporal evolution of the transient absorption/stimulated emission due to photoexcitation of LDS-821 in ACN monitored at 730 and 850 nm. At 730 nm the temporal evolution of the stimulated emission shows a fast rise with instrument response time and subsequently a growth of transient absorption with lifetime of 1.5 ps. At 850 nm the stimulated emission grows with a lifetime of 1.5 ps.

Fig. 11 shows the time-resolved transient absorption spectra obtained due to photolysis of LDS-821 in acetonitrile (ACN) in subpicosecond time-domain. In addition to the negative absorption band appearing in the 500–650 nm region due to ground state bleaching, the transient spectrum (curve 1) recorded at 0.5 ps after the pump laser pulse,

shows a weak emission band in the 650–800 nm region with a maximum at *ca* 700 nm. With increase in time delay, this emission band disappears with a concomitant development of a positive absorption band in the same region as well as another emission band in the red side of the former (i.e. in the region 800–900 nm). With increase in time delay the maximum wavelength of this new emission band shifts gradually from *ca* 800 nm, as it starts developing during *ca* 1 ps delay, to 830 nm at 10 ps, when it is fully grown. The temporal profile of the differential transient absorption monitored at 730 nm (Fig. 12) also shows the instrument response time limited rise of the stimulated emission, which subsequently disappears and is followed by the growth of a positive absorption with a lifetime of about 1.5 ± 0.2 ps. However, the temporal profile recorded at 830 nm shows a clean growth with a lifetime of 1.5 ± 0.2 ps. The inset of Fig. 11 also shows a comparison of the spectra of the transients monitored at four different times as normalized to the same peak heights. The inset shows only the changes in the shapes of the stimulated emission spectra of the transients at different time delays. At 0.5 ps the transient emission spectrum is very broad, the peak intensity extending from 670 to 750 nm. Due to overlapping of this emission band with that due to bleaching, its actual shape could not be ascertained. At later times, the width of the spectrum becomes narrower and the peak wavelength shifts to *ca* 790 nm within 1 ps and later to 830 nm after about 10 ps. Within this time-period, the growth of the emission intensity at 830 nm is also complete. However, since the bleaching band arising due to ground state depletion at 600 nm has not shown any recovery within the time up to 10 ps (temporal profile has not been shown here), the relaxation process, we observe here, must be taking place in the fluorescing state or any other excited state preceding the fluorescing state.

The excited state dynamics of LDS-821 have been monitored in a few other solvents as mentioned in Table 3. The gross features of the time-resolved transient absorption characteristics are more or less similar in other solvents as those described in case of ACN. The growth lifetime (τ_p) of the stimulated emission, obtained by single exponential fitting to the growth of the emission intensity monitored at 800–850 nm in different solvents, are given in Table 3. We observe the gradual shift of the maximum of the time-resolved stimulated emission band (which is popularly known as the dynamic Stokes' shift) only in polar solvents, but not in relatively less polar chloroform solution. Hence, the growth of the emission band, which is accompanied by the dynamics Stokes' shift, in 800–850 nm regime, could possibly be assigned to the formation of an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state and its simultaneous solvation.

In LDS-821 dye molecule (Chart 1), a hexamethine hemicyanine, the dimethylaminophenyl (donor) group is connected to the methylbenzothiazolium (acceptor) group

by a π -conjugated spacer group consisting of a polymethine chain having three ethylenic units. However, among these three ethylenic units, two are parts of a rigid cyclohexenyl ring and the other is flexible and hence only the latter is able to undergo torsional motion to take part in *trans-cis* isomerization process. The results of the reaction path computations for such a long conjugated polymethine cyanine system (e.g. penta- and heptacyanines), suggest that the ultrafast evolution of the excited state of these chromophores can be described using the two-state two-mode model⁴⁴. In this model, only the ground state (S_0) and the first excited singlet π - π^* state (S_1) are involved in the reaction. Upon excitation to the S_1 state, the molecule follows a path in which different vibrational modes are populated sequentially. The first mode is totally symmetric and drives the initially planar system out of the FC region through a skeletal stretching. The second vibrational mode is totally non-symmetric and is dominated by torsional motion about one of the central double bonds of the system. This two-mode motion, in turn, leads the system towards a *ca* 90°-twisted configuration, where the S_0 and S_1 potential energy surfaces cross at a conical intersection, thus triggering an extremely efficient $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Potential energy surface for the two-state two-mode model for the relaxation of LDS-821 molecule in the S_1 state.

The time-resolved spectra as well as the temporal dynamics of the stimulated emission monitored at different wavelengths (Figs. 10–12) mainly reveal the features of two-mode kinetic process – LE state to the TICT state. For short wavelength detection, e.g. at 730 nm, we observe the S_1 state relaxation in the region close to the FC point. The observation of a short (≤ 1 ps) rise time as well as very fast spectral evolution in this higher energy spectral regime (700–800 nm), are the signatures of the transient species evolving along the skeletal deformation coordinate in the 'valley-like' region to attain the metastable untwisted intermediate conformation, called the LE state. This process is followed by torsional motion about the free double bond ($C_1=C_2$) accompanied by the intramolecular charge transfer. The longer rise time detected at longer wavelength regime (800–850 nm) is the signature of the motion that

corresponds to torsion, leading to the TICT minimum. Hence, the growth of the stimulated emission observed at 800–850 nm wavelength regime in different solvents could be assigned primarily to the population kinetics due to LE \rightarrow TICT inter-conversion process and the parameter τ_g (Table 3) to the inverse of the rate of this process. The continuous shift of the peak of the stimulated emission band with increase in time delay observed at this wavelength regime in polar solvents indicates the solvation of the TICT state produced. This S_1 (TICT) state decays to the ground state at a much longer time scale (>300 ps).

The dynamics Stokes' shift is represented by the normalized spectral response function $C(t)$, as defined by the eq. (6)⁴⁵,

$$C(t) = \frac{v(t) - v(\infty)}{v(0) - v(\infty)} \quad (3)$$

where $v(0)$, $v(t)$ and $v(\infty)$ are the peak frequencies of the stimulated emission band due to the TICT state at zero time (i.e. in this case it is the time when the barrier crossing process just started), at time t after this zero time and at very long time when no more shift is observed, respectively. In Fig. 14, we depict $C(t)$ as a function of time for a few of the solvents. In non-alcoholic solvents (e.g. ACN and DMSO) the time behavior of $C(t)$ could be fitted to a single exponential decay function reasonably well but in alcoholic solvents (e.g. methanol and ethylene glycol) the same could be fitted well with a double exponential function. Such bimodal behavior of $C(t)$ in alcoholic solvents has been observed by many of the groups studying solvation dynamics using various kinds of probes^{41,46}. Several reasons have also been assigned to these special behavior of alcohols. However, here we are not concerned about the significance of the multi-component behavior of the solva-

Fig. 14. The normalized spectral response function, $C(t)$, are plotted as a function of time-delay, t , between the pump and the probe pulses in four solvents. The single or double exponential fit function illustrates the solvation dynamics of the TICT state formed in the S_1 state of LDS-821. In methanol and ethylene glycol, the solvation dynamics show bimodal behavior. The average solvation time, $\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{solv}}$ has been calculated by using eq. (4).

tion phenomena but only the average solvation times, $\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{solv}}$, determined either by single exponential fitting of the $C(t)$ curves or by calculating the same from the decay times obtained by double exponential fit using eq. (4)⁴⁷.

$$\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{solv}} = \frac{a_1 \tau_1 + a_2 \tau_2}{a_1 + a_2} \quad (4)$$

where τ and a represent the lifetime and the corresponding amplitude due to a particular solvation component. The $\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{solv}}$ values determined are given in Table 3 along with the corresponding values determined earlier by other groups using other kinds of probes.

It is important and interesting to compare the intramolecular charge transfer time, τ_g and the solvation time, $\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{solv}}$, observed here to the previously reported values in similar kinds of systems and also the relation between these parameters. In the case of LDS-821 molecule, Table 3 shows that the values of τ_g , the LE \rightarrow TICT conversion times, are uniformly greater than or very nearly equal to the average solvation times. Intramolecular electron transfer reaction in bianthryl, which has been studied Barbara and Jarzeba⁴⁸, provides the most convincing evidence for dynamical solvent-controlled intramolecular electron transfer process. The average electron transfer time in the S_1 state of this molecule and the average solvation time are close to an equality in each solvent. The modeling performed by these workers indicates that the intramolecular electron transfer process in bianthryl is more or less barrierless in the polar solvents. Recently, Horng *et al.*⁴⁹ have reported that the lifetimes of the LE \rightarrow CT conversion process in the excited single state of a donor substituted acridinium dye, which has been presumed to have slightly larger activation barrier in the reaction, are uniformly greater than the average solvation times.

Fig. 15A shows that the rate constants for the LE \rightarrow TICT process, i.e. τ_g^{-1} , is well correlated with the inverse of the viscosities (η^{-1}) of the solvents. The solid line in Fig. 15A is the linear fit function: $\tau_g^{-1} = 0.009 + 0.21 \eta^{-1}$ or $\tau_g^{-1} \sim 0.21 \eta^{-1}$. This simple $1/\eta$ dependence of the barrier-crossing process would correspond to a process with a much flatter and low energy barrier⁷. Fig. 15B shows that τ_g is also reasonably well correlated with $\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{coul}}$, the average (integral) solvation times of the dipolar solvation probe, C-153⁴⁹. The solvation times of C-153 have been employed here because they have been considered to represent the best measures of the timescales of polar solvation currently available, since these times are in generally good agreement with predictions of dielectric continuum models of solvation. The solid line in Fig. 15B represents the linear fit function: $\log(\tau_g) = 0.39 + 0.47 \log(\langle \tau \rangle_{\text{coul}})$.

In the present case, the average solvation times determined in the fast relaxing solvents, e.g. ACN, DMSO and DCM, the observed solvation time is longer than both τ_L as

Fig. 15. Correlation between τ_g^{-1} , $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}}$ and $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$ in different solvents. (A) Rate of formation of the TICT state (τ_g^{-1}) is linearly correlated with the inverse of the solvent viscosity, η^{-1} . The straight-line is the linear fit function, $\tau_g^{-1} = 0.009 + 0.21 \eta^{-1}$. (B) Linear correlation between (o) τ_g^{-1} or (●) $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}}$ and $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$. The solid line represents the fit function, $\tau_g^{-1} = 2.45 \langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}}^{-1}$ and the dashed line represents the unit slope of the plot, τ_g^{-1} or $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}}$ vs $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$ or the case τ_g^{-1} or $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}} = \langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$.

well as $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$ (Table 3). In slow relaxing solvents the solvation times are shorter than τ_L or $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$ and the difference between the two parameters (i.e. $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{solv}}$ and τ_L or $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$) increases as the value of the latter increases (Fig. 14B). The electron or charge transfer rates are discussed in terms of the theory of Nadler and Marcus, which addresses the role of vibrational fluctuations as well as solvent motions determining the reaction rate constant⁵⁰. If the solvent motions are controlling the observed dynamics, the experimental data should fall on the line of unit slope in the plot of τ_g^{-1} as a function of τ_L or $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$ as shown by the dashed line in Fig. 15B. As the contributions from the intramolecular modes towards the control of the charge transfer process increase, i.e. $\lambda_i > \lambda_0$ (λ_i and λ_0 are the reorganization energies due to intramolecular modes and solvent motions, respectively), the slope is predicted to decrease. In the limit $\lambda_i/\lambda_0 \rightarrow \infty$, solvent motions do not contribute to the reaction process at all and the reaction rate becomes independent of change in τ_L . We observe a large deviation of the slope of the linear fit function in the plot τ_g^{-1} as function of $\langle\tau\rangle_{\text{coul}}$, from unity (Fig. 15B). The correlations observed here lead us to conclude that, in LDS-821, the fluctuations in the intramolecular modes of the molecule make the dominant contribution to the reaction process rather than the solvent motions controlling the barrier crossing process or solvation of the excited state.

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